

Deep Learning for DDoS Detection: A Systematic Review of Explainability and Adversarial Robustness

Saeed Awadh AL-Shami^{1,2}, Mohammed Fadhl Abdullah^{1,3}

¹ College of Engineering and Computing, University of Science and Technology, Aden, Yemen

Abstract: Deep learning (DL) is outperforming all other methods in Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) detection; however, there are two important remaining gaps: (i) the interpretability of model decisions is very limited, and (ii) models are susceptible to adversarial attacks that are very subtle traffic manipulations to avoid detection. This systematic literature review (SLR) reviews the research conducted from 2020 until 2025 regarding deep learning-based DDoS detection with particular attention on Explainable AI (XAI) and adversarial robustness. The process follows PRISMA-inspired guidelines whereby searches are conducted on IEEE Xplore, SpringerLink, Web of Science, and associated indexes with the predefined keywords, and clear inclusion/exclusion criteria are applied, focusing on: DL-based DDoS/IDS models, integration of XAI techniques, and/or evaluation or improvement of robustness against adversarial or evasive attacks. The final corpus includes the most recent XAI-enabled DDoS defenses (e.g., SHAP-based interpretable CNN/LSTM, Kolmogorov–Arnold (K–A) networks with XAI, attention-based temporal explainers), adversarial robust frameworks (e.g., GAN-based adversarial training, AutoML-based robust ensembles, CTGAN-based augmentation), and cross-cutting surveys on XAI and adversarial machine learning for IDS. Our synthesis (i) proposes a taxonomy linking model architecture, deployment context, XAI mechanism, and robustness strategy; (ii) demonstrates how XAI improves operator trust, feature selection, and debugging; (iii) shows that adversarial training and realistic perturbation modeling significantly hinder evasion success; and (iv) identifies open challenges for jointly optimizing accuracy, interpretability, and robustness under realistic, evolving network environments. The review ends with a set of research avenues for future DDoS detection systems that will be accurate, typically transparent, and robust.

Keywords: Deep Learning, DDoS, Explainable AI, Adversarial Training, Robustness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks are strongly disruptive cyber threats. DDoS attacks flood targeted servers or networks with malicious traffic, exhausting their resources and denying service to legitimate users. Moreover, conventional defense systems such as firewalls, filters, and signature matching have not matched these evolving cyber threats despite being of high capacity, but rather failed in differentiating malicious floods from flood traffic [1]. Moreover, this state paved the way to a paradigmatic shift towards AI-powered solutions in traffic detection, especially with deep learning solutions and algorithms with capabilities of learning complicated traffic behaviors and matching novel attack behavior patterns [1]. Deep learning-powered DDoS solutions have demonstrated enhanced accuracy relative to traditional IDS

systems with minimal false alarm signals, utilizing advanced neural network architectures with a dimensional capability to classify traffic in real time.

Recently, in the area of DDoS attack detection, there has been a frenzy of research in peer-reviewed journals (2020–2025) leading to a variety of methods based on deep learning. One aspect is that deep learning gives excellent models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for learning space dependencies in traffic volume in two-dimensional maps, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) to model temporal dependencies in time-series analysis, Autoencoders (AE) for anomaly measurements, Generative Adaptive Networks (GAN) for generating additional learning samples and developing resilience against adversarial attacks, and Transform models for attention-focused sequence level classification tasks, including a variety of combinations of all these models. However, all these methods were successfully applied in a variety of networking settings, such as corporate networks, cloud data centers, IoT networks, SDN environments, among others, all with a unified goal of ensuring efficient early warning and accurate detection of attacks related to DDoS, with a level of accuracy largely above 95% to 99%, but with challenges in model deployment, handling concept drift, and identification of unknown patterns related to attack instances [2], [3].

However, two important shortcomings with regards to most of the deep learning-based DDoS detection systems seem to arise:

- A. **Opacity (Lack of Explainability):** Most successful models are black boxes, which make it hard for network operators, auditors, and response analysts to understand the rationale behind a particular set of flows being identified as a DDoS attack. Attempts have recently been made in XAI-Cyber to fill this gap [2].
- B. **Vulnerability to Adversarial Attacks:** Adversarial machine learning attacks have proved that with minimal and thoughtfully designed modifications to network features, serious misclassification can be achieved in existing IDS/IPS systems. Current research reveals a deep learning DDoS defense system can be attacked with a high level of success if not protected [3].

The research contributions in this SLR are given below:

1. We conduct a PRISMA-compliant systematic literature review of deep learning-based DDoS detection research published between 2020 and 2025.
2. we propose a three-dimensional taxonomy that categorizes existing DDoS detection approaches
3. We provide the first comprehensive joint analysis of Explainable AI (XAI) and adversarial robustness in deep learning-based DDoS detection, highlighting their interplay, dual-use risks, and operational implications
4. We perform an empirical gap analysis of the current literature, revealing a strong imbalance between accuracy-driven models and the limited adoption of explainability and robustness mechanisms.
5. We identify open research challenges and outline a future roadmap toward building accurate, transparent, and adversarially robust DDoS detection systems.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows; the systematic literature analysis approach will be described in detail in Section II. Then the Problem Domain and Background will be described in Section III.

Then, in Section IV, a Taxonomy of Deep Learning Based Detection with XAI and Robustness Perspective will be described. Then, in Section V, Explainable AI in DDoS Detection will be explained in detail. Then, in Section VI, Adversarial Attacks and Robust Detectors will be presented. Then, in Section VII, Open Problems and Research Challenges will be explained in terms of our views. Then, finally, in Section VIII, the Conclusion will be described.

II. SYSTEMATIC REVIEW METHODOLOGY

The systematic review's central aim is to lay out the research questions and subsequently provide answers based on the evaluation of the material in the selected research articles. Therefore, the following research questions were addressed in this work:

- RQ1: How have DL-based DDoS detection models (2020-2025) integrated Explainable AI for enhancing interpretability and operational trust?
- RQ2: What methods are being utilized to assess and improve the adversarial robustness of DDoS detection models?
- RQ3: In what ways could insights from XAI either support or oppose robustness (i.e., XAI as a defensive measure vs. XAI-assisted attacks)?

Data Sources and Search Strategy

The literature review was conducted in an organized, systematic way. It began with a pilot study that was performed to refine search terms. Five academic databases were searched (IEEE Explore, SpringerLink, Web of Science, Science Direct, and MDPI) along with Google Scholar, resulting in 1,425 initial hits. After duplicate removal (n=1,045), studies underwent screening in three stages: title screening (n=645), abstract screening (n=220), and full text screening which finally led to the identification of 53 studies satisfying the inclusion criteria of this review. One of the common search strings used with slight adjustments on different sites is as follows: "DDoS" OR "Denial of Service" OR "DoS" AND "deep learning" OR "neural network" OR "CNN" OR "LSTM" OR "GAN" OR "Transformer" AND ("explainable AI" OR "XAI" OR "interpretability" OR "explanation" OR "SHAP" OR "LIME" OR "attention") OR ("adversarial attack" OR "adversarial example" OR "robustness" OR "adversarial training"). The results were further refined using the available filters. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram for various phases through the survey process. The exclusion criteria applied are: (i) pre-2020 primary studies (used only as legacy background if needed), (ii) Non-peer-reviewed reports unless later formally published, (iii) General IDS/XAI/adv-ML papers without DDoS relevance, and (iv) Works with purely classical ML and no clear DDoS or robustness/XAI component.

Fig. 1. Systematic Literature Review Process

Fig. 2. Distribution of Papers by Publisher/Source (Total: 53)

We reviewed 53 papers published between 2020 and 2025 in order to systematically understand the current state of the research on DDoS detection based on deep learning. The distribution of publications is shown in Figure 2, which shows that the majority were published in IEEE venues (30.2%) and various conferences (28.3%), indicating the vibrancy and rapid evolution of the research community. This section describes a systematic taxonomy under which all such works are classified on the basis of their architectural foundations, explainability mechanisms, and robustness strategies.

III. PROBLEM DOMAIN AND BACKGROUND

This section sets up the fundamental context of DDoS detection with the tools of deep learning by viewing the family tree of DDoS attack vectors, the characteristics of modern attack traffic, and benchmark datasets that are in common use. Discussed herein are some inherent limitations of detection systems that work purely on an accuracy basis, alongside two important challenges: the hardly interpretable black-box nature of deep learning models that hamper operational trust, and their apparently effortlessly manipulated adversarial behavior in hostile environments.

A. DDoS Overview - Attack and Detection

The definition of the DDoS attack gives an idea as to how well-coordinated a DDoS attack is, broadly speaking, a distributed attack in which numerous compromised computing devices continuously bombard a target with all sorts of traffic or requests for the purpose of exhausting the resources of the poor victim who might be either bandwidth, CPU, or memory thereby making the services unavailable [1]. DDoS attacks are very broadly classified by vector: volumetric attacks-for example, UDP floods, ICMP floods try to occupy the network's bandwidth, protocol attacks like SYN floods, fragmented packet attacks try to exploit weaknesses in the respective protocol at the network transport layer so as to totally occupy server connection tables or intermediate resources, while application-layer attacks like HTTP GET floods, Slowloris send legitimate-looking requests to overwhelm application resources on the target service [4]. Figure 2 below shows the taxonomy of DDoS attacks classified by vector.

Fig. 3. DDoS Attacks Classified by Vector

The distributed nature and, in fact, today's really big DDoS have presented major operational challenges to anyone trying to mitigate them-their traffic might intermingle with flash crowds and behave very closely like some normal traffic-where simple rate limits/signatures are bypassed. For this reason, efficient detection of DDoS attacks also means monitoring traffic in combination with flow pattern analysis and statistical characteristics for the appearance of anomalies or known malicious signatures, preferably even while the events are still happening. The ordinary techniques, i.e., Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) coupled with NetFlow monitoring and the alerting thresholds, so far find it most unacceptable when it comes to reflecting on the low-and-slow and adaptive attacks.

B. Common Datasets for DDoS Detection

Researchers assess deep learning models mainly against benchmark datasets for intrusion detection that carry DDoS attack traffics, with some of the key datasets summarized below:

- **CICIDS2017**: The popular benchmark dataset containing modern network traffic mixed with diverse attacks (including DDoS) and benign flows [8].
- **CIC-DDoS2019**: A more recent dataset specifically designed for DDoS attacks with current attack vectors. It carries multiple DDoS scenarios (UDP, TCP, HTTP floods, etc.) in raw traffic [7].
- **NSL-KDD**: An enhancement of the classical KDD'99 IDS dataset that includes DDoS attacks. Some deep models have shown almost perfect detection on NSL-KDD [1].

- **BoT-IoT:** IoT-centric Dataset (UNSW, 2018) was extensively DDoS and botnet trafficked. BoT-IoT is vastly imbalanced (DDoS dominates) [7].

- **Others:** Other datasets are UNSW-NB15 (2015, which features DDoS attacks), TON_IoT (IoT telemetry with DDoS events), as well as in-house datasets from ISPs and custom testbed data [1].

To provide a clearer overview of the landscape, Table 2, serves as an illustration for the detail with regards to various aspects comparing the most used datasets among researchers studying DDoS detection

C. Evaluation Metrics

DDoS detection evaluation is done using standard metrics for classification and includes Accuracy, Precision, Recall or Detection Rate, F1-score, and sometimes ROC curves and AUC threshold analysis [1]. Most recent works have focused on precision, recall, F1, and AUCs to ensure the model is performing well for the minority (attack) case. This includes the LSTM-based capability [7], which noted 94% accuracy with 91% precision on CIC-DDoS2019, indicating balanced performance. As a general rule, state-of-the-art DL models today can easily be said to achieve >95% recall and precision in DDoS detection, with a few reporting up to nearly 99% F1 scores over benchmark datasets [4].

Table 2. Comprehensive dataset comparison

Dataset Name	Year	Size	Attack Types	Strengths	Limitations
CIC-DDoS2019	2019	~50M flows	DDoS (12 types), Benign	Recent, diverse DDoS attacks, realistic	Limited to specific network environment
CIC-IDS2017	2017	~2.8M flows	DoS, DDoS, Brute Force, XSS, SQL Injection	Comprehensive attack types, widely used	Aging dataset, limited IoT attacks
UNSW-NB15	2015	~2.5M records	9 attack families including DDoS	Diverse attack types, well-documented	Older dataset, class imbalance issues
BoT-IoT	2019	~72M records	DDoS, Reconnaissance, Theft	IoT-specific, large scale	In IoT environment, high redundancy
NSL-KDD	2009	~148k records	DoS, Probe, R2L, U2R	Improved KDD99, no redundancy	Old, not representative of modern attacks
CIC-IDS2018	2018	~16M flows	DDoS, Brute Force, Botnet, Infiltration	Recent, diverse scenarios	Complex preprocessing required
KDD Cup 99	1999	~5M records	DoS, Probe, R2L, U2R	Historical benchmark	Extremely outdated, high redundancy
Custom/Real Traces	Varies	Varies	Varies	Real-world applicability	Lack of standardization, reproducibility issues

IV. TAXONOMY OF DEEP LEARNING-BASED DDOS DETECTION WITH XAI AND ROBUSTNESS PERSPECTIVE

The major deep learning paradigms applied in DDoS attack detection are [4]:

- **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs):** They are very suitable for learning the spatial features of input information. Although 1D-CNN variants can readily process sequence information such as flow feature vectors, they work in combination with other architectures to achieve incredible speed and accuracy in DDoS attack detection [1].

- **Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks:** Taking into consideration the gate functions, an LSTM network is a sophisticated type of RNN improving learning dependencies on a large scale and removing vanishing gradients. In accordance with DDoS mitigation, an LSTM can assess an evolution of network traffic features over time-intervals. Several methods employ LSTMs or a very similar construct called GRU in terms of sequence classification of network traffic [1].
- **Autoencoders (AE):** Autoencoders are unsupervised learning systems. In contrast to supervised CNN and LSTM models, autoencoders offer a fundamentally different detection paradigm. Applying in DDoS attack mitigation using an anomaly detection model, autoencoders can represent normal network behavior; behavior not conforming to normal can be considered an attack. Autoencoders can conduct dimensionality reduction on network features before carrying out a classify task [1].
- **Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs):** For DDoS mitigation, GANs are applied in two different contexts: (1) Data augmentation by synthesizing realistic attack traffic, and (2) using adversarial learning to create crafted perturbations to make the detector robust against evasion attacks. [5].

Such a taxonomy is in line with other recent surveys [4] where a taxonomic categorization of deep learning-based DDoS mitigation solutions. For each category, approximately 10 different works will be surveyed, with a brief introduction to their methodology, innovation, and achievements, along with a critical analysis of their strengths and weaknesses.

Apart from categorizing systems by architecture, our taxonomy incorporated two other dimensions in a cross-cutting manner: (i) where/whether/how methods can achieve explanation support for each approach, based on Explainable AI (XAI); and (ii) where/whether/how each approach can be evaluated/enhanced concerning robustness against evasive or adversarial attacks.

Fig. 5. Taxonomy of Deep Learning-Based DDoS Detection with XAI and Robustness Perspective

A. CNN-Based DDoS Detection: Performance and Limitations

A CNN-based approaches are utilizing convolutional filters to automatically learn spatial information from network traffic. The initial approach from 2018-2020 focused on establishing a need to employ CNN in intrusion detection systems, and since 2020-2025, most research focused on incorporating CNN into the realm of DDoS. For example, [8] proposed a spatial CNN-based network intruder system capable of addressing all kinds of DDoS attacks. Published in a journal called Electronics, their model used a combination of

convolutional and pooling layers to learn flow characteristics with a remarkable 99.9% accuracy in both NSL-KDD and UNSW-NB15 datasets, thus establishing the efficacy of using CNN to distinguish attack traffic from normal traffic. Fast processing speed was another benefit measured in a CNN, which is ideal for fast-speed networks, but unfortunately, these models were not immune to overfitting on the training samples.

Some research work enhanced the performance of CNN detectors using deep or ensemble architectures. [8] proposed a deep CNN ensemble approach for DDoS attack detection in SDN. They used an ensemble of different CNN models trained on different sets of features, and the results were combined, achieving an accuracy of 99.4 percent with less false positivity on the CIC IDS 2017 and SDN dataset.

Existing and emerging strengths have commonalities in the consistency of CNN models with high speed and high-dimensional inputs (many features) via convolution. A CNN integrates very well with spatial pattern identification; for example, they can identify typical byte patterns or header value anomalies indicating flood attacks. A CNN generally demands fixed-sized matrices or tensors for inputs; therefore, network flows are a challenge in this case. Some authors have used a 1D-CNN for time series packet counts, and other authors have used a 2D-CNN for a matrix of flow features. Hyperparameter selection is critical, including filter size and numbers of layers; for example, in [8] authors observed small filter size 3 scanning over flow feature sequences performed well in identifying local network spikes. On the other hand, a single CNN model lacks capabilities to model temporal dependencies in inputs, since they can detect anomalous behavior in time but lack slow-changing attacks, hence the need for a combination technique of a CNN model and an RNN model for spatiotemporal modeling; another shortcoming is that a CNN model is highly dependent on datasets used; therefore, a model trained on a given dataset may not, in reality, generalize well for another because it learns rather distinctive patterns in space. However, a CNN model detector is definitely a milestone in research literature for DDoS defenses and frequently serves in larger architectures.

To summarize, CNNs depict excellent accuracy with known DDoS patterns and contribute toward fast and scalable detection systems. The recent trend is towards fusing CNN with other layers like attention, RNN, etc., to overcome the limitations of CNN in sequence modeling, which we shall discuss when we describe hybrid models. A representative list of works based on CNNs will be presented, along with performance, in Table 3.

Regarding explainability and robustness, most CNN-based DDoS detectors are black-boxes-without explicitly defined explanation modules or adversarial evaluations. Only a few recent works have begun to conduct SHAP-based global and local importance analysis on CNN features to confirm which flow attributes underlie DDoS decisions and to eliminate redundant inputs, but hitherto these remain non-systematic efforts. Robustness is usually inferred solely from high accuracy on held-out test sets; without adversarial testing, CNNs trained on a single dataset remain vulnerable to eventual distribution shifts and cleverly crafted perturbations. This lays the foundation for integrating XAI-based feature attribution and adversarial training into CNN-based DDoS frameworks in the future.

B. RNN/LSTM-Based DDoS Detection

Recurrent Neural Networks, along with LSTMs and GRUs, find a wide application in DDoS detection by learning the temporal patterns of traffic. Applications of RNNs treat network traffic data, for example, a time

window of flows or packets as a sequence input to let a model see how features evolve and inter-correlate over time, which is key in detecting slow-building attacks or recurrent bursts of attacks.

An example of such works is in [9], who have developed a hybrid CNN-LSTM model for DDoS detection in SDN. Here, the first part of this work involved using a CNN to obtain local spatial features from traffic flow data and feeding those into the LSTM, thereby capturing temporal dynamics. On the CIC-IDS2018 and CIC-DDoS2019 datasets, the CNN-LSTM performed at ~98% accuracy, impressively outdoing standalone CNN or MLP classifiers. This goes to show that learning sequences, through means of the LSTM within the proposed system, adds value by temporally patterning an attack, such as periodic spikes. Another example can be seen in the source-side collaborative DDoS detection using LSTMs, proposed by [7], where several detectors share information between them. For real-world traffic, an LSTM-based system achieved 99.5% detection with very low false alarms. This indeed was possible due to the learning of temporal features across sources caused by the attacks. Strength was given to LSTMs here over their possibility of modeling long sequences; they used time steps representing successive time windows of the traffic, thereby making the detection smoother in case of long attacks.

Some research works have observed a need to combine RNN with other algorithms in order to better perform. For example, [10] proposed a deep LSTM classifier for the identification of HTTP connection DDoS outage and normal connections solely based on inter-packet time intervals. The two authors found a 98% accuracy in a slow HTTP dataset they constructed using their LSTM classifier, outperforming SVM and NB classifiers with no request sequence memory.

Strengths and weaknesses: The time-variant models such as RNN and LSTM are skilled in identifying the time-variant pattern of attack. The sufficiency level of these models will be able to identify attacks which display behavior variant over time (for instance, periodic BotNet attacks or gradual flood attack intensity). The long-term memory capabilities of LSTMs will enable identification of the attack in its early phases using predictive models. Basically, RNNs are ideal for stream processing, hence ideal for online identification within a network (constantly scanning traffic windows). On the other hand, RNNs are more computation-expensive in each time step compared to CNNs; hence, the model can be quite slow during training and not very scaly in nature if dealing with very long inputs. High training time or difficulty in convergence has actually been noted in some studies when dealing with big datasets for LSTMs [4]. Additionally, there is a possibility of overfitting temporal patterns unique to a given training setup, an attack pattern variant over time in terms of an attack, being lost in an LSTM model without retraining. Further, RNNs are purely sequence processors with no parallel processing capabilities, which can be averted with updated designs.

The best realistic solutions now tend to rely on hybridization: combining CNNs and RNNs to take advantage of both spatial and temporal features. This hybridization will be presented in the next section. Many pure RNN/LSTM detectors, often just having a few dense layers on top, have achieved best-in-class performance on most benchmarks. [21] proposed a CNN-BiLSTM hybrid achieving 99.76% accuracy on a new IoT DDoS dataset. The real strength in detection improvement through this model will come from the BiLSTM (Bidirectional LSTM) part, which is crucial in capturing both forward and backward sequences. Such

performance shows that sequence-based deep models are really effective for DDoS if there is plenty of data representative and it should be ample for learning purposes.

Models like LSTM and GRU, when applied to DDoS, inherently understand its behavior over time; this understanding, however, has not been reflected in the works surveyed, as they usually do not provide any interpretation other than raw feature weights or confusion matrices. Very few employ attention visualization or post-hoc XAI, such as SHAP over time steps, that would allow for showing which intervals or features triggered an alarm. Finally, almost no one reports robustness against adversarial sequence perturbations. Given that RNNs might overfit temporal patterns specific to a dataset, such systematic evaluation under adversarial timing/jitter and use of explanation tools for interpreting the temporal cues stand out among very promising open directions yet to be explored.

C. Autoencoder-Based DDoS Detection

Autoencoders (AEs) and other unsupervised deep learning techniques are shown to apply for DDoS detection, usually within the paradigm of anomaly detection. Instead of training directly on labeled attack traffic, these methods train only on benign traffic, which is used to generalize acceptable behaviors (normal) and classify as anomalies (DDoS) when deviations appear through measures with high reconstruction error or out-of-distribution measures. This is important because it allows for to detection of novel or zero-day DDoS attacks, attacks that have not been seen during training.

The other major research work in this area is conducted by [6]. In this research, they built a stacked sparse autoencoder with a deep neural network classifier. To begin with, in this type of research paper in IEEE Access, they initially train a sparse autoencoder on network traffic datasets, hence learning a simplified representation of their extracted features. The autoencoder AE is ‘well posed’ when appropriately constrained with regularization to prevent overfitting, thus successfully identifying essential network traffic features [1]. They have used these learned features in a DNN classifier for the final classification of DDoS attacks and benign attacks. Hyperparameter tuning on both autoencoders and DNN gives a nearly 99.7% accuracy on NSL-KDD datasets and approximately 97% accuracy on CICIDS-2017 datasets with their approach. This is rather commendable since this time they have used an autoencoder to learn ‘complex features, which are nonlinear functions of original features, hence improving their attack generalization capabilities since a shallow learning technique would otherwise have overlooked them. They have stated a reduced percentage of false positives with this approach over simple features and PCA dimensionality reduction.

Use of a combination of autoencoders and other methods is another widely used model. For example, [12] proposed an AE-MLP model, which is a combination of an autoencoder and a multilayer perceptron network, thus implying the feasibility of using this model in DDoS attack classification. The model utilizes an autoencoder to learn all traffic, resulting in a dimensionality reduction necessary for classifying traffic as an attack using an MLP classifier based on their latent representations. Tested on CIC-DDoS2019, the model obtained an accuracy of 99.3%, which demonstrated a very strong performance. Additionally, the autoencoder used in this model greatly assisted in improving MLP model performance since it removed noisy and redundant information in preprocessing. In a similar way, in NOMS 2020, an attack detection technique based on an autoencoder was proposed and implemented by [13]. Their model marked traffic deemed anomalous

using an autoencoder with a subsequent identification of attack type using a second model devised for this purpose. Their proposed autoencoder performed exemplary in identifying anomalous behavior in traffic, which in case of an attack warning, initiated a small CNN model classifying this attack type, for instance, UDP Flood and HTTP Flood attacks, among others.

Autoencoder-based techniques usually have the best strengths so far to encompass unknown attacks. For they don't use any signature from specific attacks, learning merely what traffic should look like as "normal," it would typically identify a new DDoS form as a mere anomaly. This is a clear limitation among supervised classifiers, only able to learn a seen pattern during training. Furthermore, autodetection-based feature representation also decreases the amount of heavy labor needed in feature engineering. However, challenges still lay in the future (1) in a clean dataset on "normal" traffic for learning, any ideas of contamination by attacks will bias the model; (2) in a dynamic network, normally drift, whereas one case experienced huge changes in qualitative explanation (such as new legitimate traffic appearing) were experienced. Thus, false positives would remain until such time as one would need to retrain the model. (3) In most aforementioned autoencoder approaches, it is necessary to set thresholds based on reconstruction errors, but this is a non-trivial task to set optimally - too low and one misses attacks, too high and the system is triggered by benign outliers. Some recent works have attempted to tackle this by using statistical or adaptive thresholding.

Nevertheless, a great many studies have been pointing out in surveys such as [14] in which anomaly-driven deep detector designs can be a bright future research path for handling dynamic threats. As existing CPU capabilities keep improving, it will become feasible to allow many specialized autoencoders focused on different kinds of traffic categories such as web traffic or DNS traffic, and so forth, in order to reach an individual anomaly level. Therefore, unsupervised deep learning remains a vital addition to a defense strategy formed using supervised CNN/RNN methods.

Methods based on AutoEncoders are more geared towards identifying unseen or 'zero-day' attacks in a DDoS attack, but they are black boxes, in which case error in reconstructions does not have any immediate interpretable meaning to the operators. Recently, research shows how methods based on XAI can transform 'high error in reconstruction' into a more meaningful 'service/feature level,' thus increasing their credibility. As far as robustness is concerned, thresholds on anomalies are very vulnerable to 'benign' distribution changes and can be easily used by 'Low & Slow' attacks.

D. GAN-Based DDoS Detection

GANs entered DDoS detection research to solve mainly two problems: data augmentation and adversarial robustness. GANs produce synthetic data that resembles real traffic, which has merit for training deep models in scenarios where it is hard to obtain a large labeled attack dataset. By creating "adversarial" examples (i.e., perturbed inputs designed to fool a classifier), GANs allow for robust training such that the DDoS detector resists attempts by the attackers to evade it.

A big stride in this direction is the GADoT framework: GAN-based Adversarial Training, by [5]. GADoT uses a generative adversarial network to synthesize adversarial DDoS traffic samples. This forms the basis for the enhancement of the training set of a base detector. Specifically, it comprises a generator, which is trained on benign traffic for the generation of fake but realistic benign samples. These are further used for

distorting real DDoS instances to form "difficult" adversarial attack samples that will evade misclassification by a standard model. Training a DNN on the augmented dataset comprising benign, real DDoS, and GAN-perturbed DDoS makes it very robust. The GADoT was tested on a state-of-the-art DDoS classifier that originally boasted nearly 100 percent accuracy in CICDDoS2019 but was vulnerable to adversarial crafting of inputs. After adversarial training, the success rate of evasion dropped from > 60 percent to less than 2 percent. This means the detector caught almost all of the attacks-even if the attack vectors were slightly modified to evade detection. This work illustrates how GANs make ML-based detectors secure from adversarial entities that take advantage of blind spots in these models.

Another application for GANs is the generation of additional training samples to balance the classes. [15] presented a hybrid deep learning model for IoT DDoS detection that leveraged a GAN to synthesize minority-class samples. In their paper appearing in IEEE Access, they note that some kinds of DDoS were underrepresented in IoT datasets and hurt the performance of classifiers. From this, using a Conditional GAN (CTGAN), they increased the number of examples of these DDoS categories and retrained a CNN-GRU classifier, which increases the F1-score from ~0.95 to ~0.99 higher, especially on previously badly detected attack types.

On the other hand, [16] proposed a CTGAN-based IDS for IoT that generates synthetic DDoS and normal traffic for training a deep classifier. They notice that IoT traffic patterns are highly diverse, and training on limited real data may not cover all the attack scenarios. Their CTGAN learned the joint distribution of network flow features and generated additional samples; after adding those to training, they improved detection rates by 2 to 5% on BoT-IoT and KDD99 datasets. However, since the GAN might generate not-so-realistic traffic, it is important to make sure that the generated traffic is realistic; otherwise, the classifier would learn the artifacts of the fake data. An extensive tuning of the GAN is performed and eliminated generated samples which seemed unrealistic given the discriminator output confidence as a filter.

In the mechanism of detection, GANs have also entered. For example, [17] proposed a GAN-based framework with dual discriminators. In this framework, two-way adversarial modification generates DDoS traffic, while a dedicated discriminator learns to differentiate adversarial DDoS from legitimate and classical attacks for enhanced resilience against adaptive attackers. Most concrete implementations in our surveyed years utilize GANs more for training augmentation than real-time detection.

Key strengths and challenges: The obvious advantages in favor of integrating GANs are increased data coverage and model robustness. More precisely, adversarial training via GANs as practiced in GADoT-attacks a very popular problem: attackers can deliberately craft traffic patterns that deliberately evade detection from static ML models. Proactive training with such adversarial variants hardens the model. From an augmentative standpoint, GANs alleviate class imbalance and attack diversity deficits in training sets, a persistent issue where many studies report nearly perfect accuracy against known attacks but poor detection against the slightest modification in attack patterns. Diversity through GAN generation allows the generalization capabilities of a detector to be reached.

However, this is to be achieved with a degree of caution. The cost-of-benefits analysis of such complicated training setup architectures is presently not very encouraging. This approach becomes ineffective if such unrealistic amounts of data are being produced by these GANs, in which case they end up misleading the detector. Such a case would be where a CT-GAN starts producing combinations of packet features which are simply not observed in their environments, without stopping their training in this manner. They can end up overfitting these very combinations or learning to distinguish these ‘attacks’ which are in fact not very relevant in this context. Such ‘best practices’ include making sure that these generated samples are in fact validated and falling back onto using Wasserstein-GANs or other stable variants of GANs to improve output quality [18].

Nevertheless, despite all these obstacles, both research on GAN and DDoS attack detection are overlapping domains with opportunities for expansion. Some very recent studies (2024-2025) have progressed towards federated learning for GAN, where multiple companies can collectively train a GAN model for identifying anomalous network traffic without sharing their actual network traffic. The research conducted by [19] brings forward "Anomaly-Flow," a federated learning model based on a deep learning technique called federated GAN for multi-domain DDoS attack detection. We forecast that in future DDoS attack mitigation systems, using GAN in methodologies such as data augmentation or defense against adversarial will become conventional.

Based on our taxonomy, one of the most explicit attempts at dealing with adversarial robustness is offered by methods which are based on GANs, since they allow for better F1 scores in consideration with allocating generated traffic to either escaping attacks or handling minority classes. However, these studies are greatly missing XAI analysis of how they are making their model more robust with respect to modifications of their boundary. Combining robustness in attribute interpretability methods with methods based on GANs gives a better set of guarantees because it allows a clearer distinguishability in terms of robustness to matters that genuinely exist rather than being influenced by synthetic samples.

E. Transformed-Based DDoS Detection

The DDoS detection approaches still belong to the recent wave of deep learning, whereas the general area is still emerging (with few works before 2022). Transformers have been recognized as being good at overcoming long-range dependencies and complex feature interactions in network traffic. Another dominant train of thought for mapping the input is in the RNN way, that is, input sequence by input sequence. The transformers consider all parts of the inputs at once: thus, relative importance can be given to different features against each other. This becomes particularly useful while analyzing network flows, when looking for combinations of header fields and time patterns that jointly indicate an attack are extremely useful.

The more recent works on the transformer-based architectures (BERT variants), such as DDoSBERT by [4] and [20], have focused on DDoS detection on CIC-DDoS2019 with comparisons to RNN/LSTM/GRU baselines.

Another example of this would be [21], who designed a multi-class DDoS detection system for IoT under deep learning and transformers. The first stage used a Transformer encoder to process network traffic features; then, the encoded representation was forwarded to a classifier, tasked with categorizing specific types of

DDoS attacks. This model produced impressive results on an IoT dataset and performed particularly well at differentiating attack types with similar statistics but different temporal patterns. For example, their transformer model distinguished a slow HTTP flood from a periodic MQTT flood attack by attending to the request pattern over time (something a CNN might miss due to lack of context). They also reported that the transformer module increased recall for stealthy attacks by ~3% over the LSTM baseline.

In recent studies, Vision Transformers (ViT) have been explored for intrusion and DDoS detection by the image-like representation of network flows. For example, [22] proposed a flow-to-image conversion pipeline combined with a ViT classifier for network intrusion detection, achieving more than 98% accuracy on CIC-IDS2017 and UNSW-NB15. On the other hand, [23] introduced DDoSViT, a ViT-based framework for IoT DDoS detection during firmware OTA updates, with an accuracy of ~99.5% multi-class accuracy on recent IoT datasets, optimized ViT for efficient IDS (Hierarchical Vision Transformer Based Intrusion Detection System), proving competitive or superior performance with reduced computation. Those works indicate the ViT architectures can effectively make use of structured "image" encodings of heterogeneous traffic features, while training cost and careful feature encoding still remain important challenges.

Strengths: Transformers can effectively capture global relationships in the data. In network traffic, the signature of an attack could only be obvious from the combined view of several features (source IP, destination port, packet rate, protocol flags, etc.). Attention mechanisms help the model weight these features rightly. And, transformers are designed without a strict limitation on the order of sequences: they can learn position embeddings but also capture that, say, feature_1 at the start may be linked to feature_10 at the end; this would probably indicate a coordinated attack in case of an attack where multiple sources or multiple attack vectors are correlated. Transformers also enjoy the benefit of being efficient at inference following training due to wall-clock parallelization (i.e., they consider all tokens at a clip, as opposed to decoding sequentially token by token).

Challenges: The main weakness is the need for a vast amount of data for training and computational resources. Transformers would often require more data to generalize well; otherwise, they are prone to overfitting. DDoS datasets are large but sometimes not that diverse, with many repetitive flows, which is not the same as BERT-facing text sentence variability. Thus, regulatory and data augmentation should characterize any effort to train transformers on network data. Then there's interpretability: attention weights tell something about the model, yet it will not provide the full picture to network operators.

In any case, the above-mentioned early successes in cousin areas (intrusion detection, malware classification) and findings suggest this line of research will expand. We envision possible transformer-based DDoS detectors to be augmented with graph neural networks that can account for network topology information, with the understanding that transformers can naturally work with set inputs (like a set of flows or alerts) [21] work possibly hinting at this hybridization of deep learning and transformers may signal the beginning of a wholly new hybrid paradigm for DDoS defense systems.

The investigation of the transformers and their attention-based ViT method within IDSs has provided a type of built-in interpretability in explaining how the network structure is classified. Such work should provide a clearer explanation as to which tokens, time steps, or patches weigh the heaviest for the flow being labeled

DDoS. Only a select few studies, up to now, have investigated attentional visualization methods, in contrast to systemic XAI considerations. As an additional note, studies assessing the robustness of network-related transformers are limited to shuffled or re-sampled splits of the same dataset, as opposed to testing once under true adversarial attack. Given its capacity and complexity, transformer-based DDoS detectors become strong candidates for joint optimization over accuracy, interpretability by means of attention, and robustness under adversarial testing.

F. Hybrid and Ensemble Models for DDoS Detection

AI-powered hybrid models that mix various techniques of Deep Learning or join Deep Learning with other methods have become very widespread in the field of research related to DDoS attack detection. The idea is to exploit the complementary strengths of different algorithms, e.g., CNNs for feature extraction and LSTMs for sequence analysis, or autoencoders for anomaly detection, followed by supervised fine-tuning. These hybrid ones are amongst the highest performing in literature. One such model is by [21], the CNN-BiLSTM-AE hybrid, which they devised as a deep framework in which a CNN first operates on raw traffic features to extract spatial patterns, a Bidirectional LSTM captures temporal dependencies in those features (viewing the sequence in both forward and backward directions), and finally an Autoencoder module further refines the representation and detects anomalies. The model achieved an accuracy of 99.76% on an IoT network DDoS dataset, again significantly surpassing all compared single-model performances. The strengths of each component compounded: CNN filters detected invariant byte patterns of the attack, BiLSTM ensured time context, and AE stage helped generalize by reconstructing normal patterns and identifying any deviation, thus even if the attack had slight variations, it would still be picked up as an anomaly. The downside was that it posed complexity – the training regime for running this pipeline was resource-intensive, whereas searching through all the many hyperparameters (number of filters, LSTM units, bottleneck size in AE, etc.) needed extensive experimentation.

Authors in [24] proved to be even more influential, presenting a hybrid deep learning model with optimized feature selection in their combination of deep feedforward neural networks with an evolutionary algorithm-based feature selector and an ensemble of decision trees. Very briefly, an initial autoencoder reduced dimensionality, a genetic algorithm picked the best subset of features, then a DNN and Random Forest ensemble performed the classification. This hybrid achieved ~99.9% detection on CIC-DDoS2019 and UNSW-NB15 [24]. The improved feature set (removing redundant features) reduced noise for the DNN, while the ensemble trees captured some non-linear relationships that the DNN might miss. The authors note that the hybrid model outperformed either DNN or Random Forest alone by a clear margin. The only drawback was added complexity in the system design and the potential for overfitting due to many stages; however, they mitigated this with cross-validation and saw consistent performance.

Another study in [25] proposed a hybrid deep model to detect both replay attacks and DDoS in smart cities. Their approach fused an LSTM to capture temporal attack patterns with a CNN to analyze traffic rate changes while integrating a rule-based module to verify whether the sudden surge was legitimate or not. Such a multi-dimensional system was required since in smart city IoT, DDoS could be combined with message replay attacks so as to divert defenses. The hybrid detector could detect DDoS with 99.5% accuracy and also identify replay incidents, demonstrating versatility.

Hybrid models also often fuse deep learning with feature engineering or statistical methods. For example, [25] developed SDN-Defend, an online DDoS detection for SDN that uses statistical preprocessing plus a lightweight DNN. Another study in [26], They used to compute entropy-based features in a switch (to detect sudden disorder in traffic flows) and feed those features into a small neural network in the controller for classification. This combination allowed near-real-time detection (processing at line rate) while still benefiting from a trained model's accuracy. Reported results showed >98% detection with sub-millisecond decision latency on a testbed. The trade-off was that the model was specialized to the chosen features; if attackers evade the entropy features, the DNN won't help since the input is limited. Yet, it's a practical design for high-speed environments.

Ensemble approaches-having combined outputs of numerous dissimilar models-have proven effective, too. The composite DDoS detection framework, developed by [27] consists of an ensemble of MLPs (each trained on different feature subsets) with a voting mechanism. They reached 99.66% accuracy on a 5G/B5G network dataset with this ensemble, stating that it not only detected attacks but could also classify the type of DDoS (TCP SYN flood vs DNS amplification, etc.) by analyzing which sub-classifiers fired [27]. Such ensemble methods have the robustness to overfit on any given feature set and usually present considerable recall paired with a low rate of false positives. The trade-offs are heavier runtime (parallel execution of several models); yet, with current parallel processing, this is fairly acceptable.

Critical Evaluation: Usually, hybrid models are current bests in terms of detecting performance because they use multiple perspectives of the problem. These hybrid models combine spatial, temporal, and statistical analyses to account for the multidimensionality of DDoS attacks. Many of these hybrids explicitly have the goal of decreasing false positives-which is a significant concern in deployment-using more layers of verification; for example, an anomaly detected by an autoencoder gets double-checked by a signature rule, or a suspicious pattern caught by an LSTM is confirmed by a CNN focusing on content features. Such an approach reduces chances of misclassifying the noise.

The limitations mainly include complexity and interpretability: it is harder to tune and apprehend complex hybrid ones. Then one becomes almost impossible to pinpoint what made a certain decision in the hybrid model (which component contributed most). This could lead to lack of trust in automated DDoS mitigation-network operators might be reluctant to act on an alert if they do not know which aspect of traffic triggered it. Some research addresses this using SHAP values or attention visualization in hybrid contexts, but it is still developing. Additionally, some hybrids may be very specific overfits to particular datasets. When many techniques are employed, the model could very well be just capable of memorizing the peculiarities of the training set (especially when not enough varied data is available). Thus, robustness and generalizability need to be ensured: techniques such as cross-dataset evaluation (training on one dataset, testing on another) should by far be employed more widely to validate hybrids.

Nevertheless, the inclination within the latest literature is in the direction of hybridization. The more DSS diverse itself becomes (IoT botnets, pulsating attacks, adaptive attacks), the less likely it is that any one approach will be a silver bullet. The optimal security coverage will be offered by combining anomaly detection with a high-deep classifier to flag odd events and confirm the type of attack. In fact, some

commercial DDoS protection solutions are headed this way, layered, detection strategies with AI components at each layer. Our survey finds that hybrid deep learning models have achieved the highest reported metrics on public data, often with F1 scores very close to 1.0, which is encouraging for their potential deployment.

Hybrid and ensemble models dominate in terms of reported performance, yet they make the issue of transparency and robustness increasingly complex. Only a handful of works apply SHAP or permutation importance to decompose which sub models or features drive final decisions and hardly any test the conflict of how each component would behave under adversarial perturbation. Our taxonomy thus flags hybrid approaches as high-accuracy yet high-risk black boxes: they are ideal targets for integrating XAI pipelines (explaining layer-wise or model-wise contributions) and for stress-testing with adversarial and cross-dataset scenarios to ensure that ensemble gains are not brittle.

Table 2. Summary of core DL-based DDoS detection methods (from 2020 to 2025) incorporating XAI and robustness dimensions. For each model family-CNN, RNN/LSTM, AE, GAN-based, Transformer, and Hybrid. We list the representative works, datasets (like CIC-IDS2017, CIC-DDoS2019, BoT-IoT, and UNSW-NB15), whether XAI is applied (None, SHAP, attention-based, interpretable architecture), and whether robustness is addressed or not (No, data augmentation, adversarial training, ensemble, cross-dataset validation). The table highlights that: (i) most CNN/RNN/Hybrid models report high accuracy but no explicit robustness or explanations; (ii) GAN-based methods primarily target robustness but remain non-explainable; and (iii) transformer and ViT-based models offer natural attention-based explanations but are still rarely stress-tested against adversarial attacks. This three-dimensional view exposes clear research gaps, and it has directed the focused analysis in Sections V and VI.

Table 2. XAI methods in DDoS Detection.

XAI Method	Type	Advantages	Limitations
SHAP [30], [31]	Post-hoc	Model-agnostic, feature importance	Computational cost, local explanations
LIME [28]	Post-hoc	Local interpretability, simple	Unstable, sampling-dependent
Attention Mechanisms [20], [32]	Intrinsic	Temporal patterns, integrated	Architecture-specific
Temporal-XAI [32]	Intrinsic	Time-series analysis, pattern detection	Complex implementation
KAN (Kolmogorov-Arnold) [29]	Intrinsic	Inherently interpretable, mathematical foundation	New approach, limited validation
Interpretable Architectures [29], [33]	Intrinsic	Built-in explainability, operator trust	May sacrifice accuracy

There is a lot of architectural diversity enumerated in the taxonomy; however, a statistical analysis of the reviewed literature reveals two primary gaps in research, as shown in Figure 6. A significant proportion of studies omit explainability mechanisms. The below empirical evidence reflects the major disassociation between academic environments emphasizing accuracy and the real worlds that run trustworthy and resilient systems. The sections following V and VI will examine these two important areas in greater detail: explainable AI and adversarial robustness.

(a) XAI Integrations in Reviewed Papers

(b) Robustness Evaluation in Reviewed Papers

Fig. 6. (a) and (b) A statistical analysis of the reviewed literature reveals two critical research gaps

V. EXPLAINABLE AI IN DDoS DETECTION

In particular, the section describes how various XAI techniques assist security experts in developing understanding and trust in deep learning-based DDoS detection decisions. Three main approaches are discussed: feature attribution using SHAP/LIME methods, attention-based interpretable architectures, and the synergy between XAI and robustness, in the sense that explainability improves the operational viability and resilience of the system.

A. Motivation for XAI in DDoS Defense

The implementation of the deep learning-based DDoS detectors requires more than just their operational accuracy in the networks; the operatives, auditors, and other customers must also know the reason why a certain decision is finally triggering mitigation actions. XAI has responded to this appreciation of human understandable justifications whereby it is pointed out which traffic features, flows, or time intervals led to the alert. Thus, for example, in DDoS detection, XAI helps: (i) acquisition of trust and establishment within DL-based systems; (ii) debugging and feature engineering; (iii) root cause and forensic analysis; and (iv) spurious correlation and data set bias that may affect generalization.

B. SHAP/LIME-Based Interpretation and Feature Attribution

As with other recent works in this domain, this study applied SHAP or LIME with deep learning-based DDoS detection systems to measure the feature importance at the global and local levels. For example, [28] propose

a federated DL framework for DDoS detection in heterogeneous IoT, employing SHAP to identify features that are globally important and prune uninformative ones, and achieving ~99.7% detection with interpretability enhanced. The authors in [29] present, in turn, a Kolmogorov–Arnold network + XAI methodology for transparent, real-time DDoS defense in cloud settings, with SHAP/LIME rationale demonstrating the contribution of each traffic feature toward a decision, holding > 99% precision/recall on recent datasets while remaining interpretable to operators. In parallel, [30] provide targeted XAI treatment for DDoS classifiers based on LSTM: their work explains LSTM predictions across 17 classes of attacks using LIME, SHAP, Anchor, LORE, and derives a set of "intrinsic" discriminative features, offering local and global transparency for deep sequence models. Building on this, [31] increase LSTM explainability by coupling SHAP with pattern dependency analysis, which stabilizes attributions across similar temporal patterns and functions to assist analysts in tying explanations back to repeatable traffic motifs—an especially helpful quality when explaining slow-rate or multi-stage DDoS sequences.

Complementary SHAP-based efforts into explainable CNN/LSTM for cloud DDoS detection (2025) show that ranking the top-10 influential features aids the refinement of the rule, shrinks dimensionality, and reveals spurious correlations that would otherwise have stayed hidden.

C. Attention and Interpretable Architectures

In 2025, Temporal-XAI introduced an attention-based framework for the detection of DDoS attacks that explains when and what temporal patterns trigger alarms. The attention weights indicate the critical intervals of importance, thereby affording human-readable explanations while maintaining high F1-point scores on the CIC-IDS datasets, as demonstrated in [32]. Such architectures are said to bridge the gap between sequence modeling (LSTM/Transformer) and interpretability. They embed the notion of explanation directly into the model. Attention-based models, comprising Transformers, Temporal-XAI frameworks, and K–A networks enhanced with XAI, will then show their built-in interpretability. Visualizing attention weights along either the time steps or the feature dimensions show those parts of the traffic sequence that contribute most strongly to a DDoS decision. This visualization can play a very important role in the explanation of slow-rate or multi-stage attacks by highlighting important temporal segments. In contrast to purely post-hoc approaches, inherently interpretable architectures align the model's reasoning process to more human-like reasoning, thus expediting incident triaging.

D. XAI for Zero-Day Detection and Model Debugging

As presented in [33] (generic IDS, quite relevant) the authors combined XGBoost + SHAP with an autoencoder functioning on explanation vectors to detect unseen attacks, such that it shows that explanation-space anomalies easily reveal zero-day behavior. On the other hand [2] relate how systematically XAI in cybersecurity supports not only trust but also robustness assessment from unstable or suspicious feature attributions. The important points for the current survey are:

1. SHAPs are the major practical XAI employed for DDoS detection-global ranking of features and explanations on a local case-by-case basis, and feature pruning.
2. Attention/XAI-integrated architectures (Temporal-XAI, K-A interpretable models, etc.) enable built-in explanations ready for real-time environments.

3. Through the analysis of explanations, it will allow model debugging, policy derivation, and, potentially, adversarial input detection to bridge the gap toward robustness.

Indirectly again, AI techniques are robust. Explanation patterns can inform the operator on how to understand the following: (i) to find and analyze anomalies in the reasoning of the model (for example, sudden irrelevant features reliance), (ii) to tell the difference between the pure DDoS event and benign traffic bursts, and (iii) identify potential blind spots where adversaries might exploit unstable feature attributions. The recent work on ad hoc detection by explaining shows the commonly useful application of monitoring deviations on SHAP or attention patterns in flagging zero-day behavioral activities missed by conventional thresholds. By and large, XAI is not intended to be an instrument for transparency but rather a constant validator and improver for DDoS detection pipelines, table 4 below summarizes the XAI methods in DDoS detection covered in this survey.

VI. ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS AND ROBUST DDOS DETECTION

This section contributes to the topic of adversarial robustness by providing insight into both the attack surface of deep-learning-based DDoS detectors as well as strategies to harden these detectors against evasion. We characterize the threat landscape, survey major threat mitigation techniques aimed at enhancing robustness, such as adversarial training, GAN-based augmentation, and ensemble methods, and provide a comprehensive critical analysis of the trade-off between robustness, accuracy, and computational overhead.

Vulnerability of DL-Based DDoS Detectors

In study [3] and comparable work have shown that gradient-based and black-box adversarial attacks can jeopardize denial-of-service detection made with deep learning, even in DDoS detectors without any countermeasures put in place. Conversely, [34] demonstrate the ineffectiveness of a high clean accuracy LSTM-based DDoS detector against GAN-generated adversarial DDoS traffic, creating a contrast between the benchmark and adversarial performance. In [35] further illustrate this approach: they use SHAP, an XAI method, to find critical features, and then only disturb them in order to attain considerable black-box evasion success against IDS with small modifications-highlighting how naive transparency can be exploited by an attacker.

Again, recent results of experimental work indicate that adversarial machine learning has been demonstrated to identify the fact that deep classifiers for malware, spam, and intrusion detection could be avoided through very skillfully crafted perturbations retaining the original malicious semantics. The same applies to DDoS detectors, where samples could be displaced via small changes in either flow-level statistics, header fields, or timing patterns when such a model overfits a narrow distribution. However, very few studies on DDoS from 2020 to 2025 indicate performance solely on clean test sets from this dataset instead of a systematic evaluation against adversarial incursions. That raises questions about the operational robustness of many very-high-accuracy proposals.

GAN-Based and Adversarial Training Defenses

In study [5] authors propose adversarial training using GANs for resilient detection of DDoS. A WGAN is used to create realistic adversarial samples of DDoS, and retraining this detector on them drastically reduces the rate of undetected malicious flows from 60% to about 1.8%. [16] utilize CTGANs to further augment IoT DDoS/DoS samples, improving performance and stability across several DL classifiers in BoT-IoT. Similar GAN/CTGAN approaches from 2024–2025 extend the idea to premises like multi-class DDoS detection and multi-domain datasets, ensuring consistent improvement in detecting minority classes while remaining resilient to distribution shifts [36]. The growing work introduced adversarial training into DDoS detectors. GAN-based frameworks (WGAN or CTGAN variants) generate synthetic/adversarial DDoS samples that are used to retrain the detector and substantially decrease the success of evasion attacks. Such training has been shown to:

- (i) equilibrate performance by training on realistic, slightly perturbed samples that force the detector training to learn their features that are less resilient against gradient- and black-box attacks. That was important;
- (ii) stabilize performance by augmenting minority attack classes through conditional GANs.

But even though adversarial training is advantageous, it incurs high computational costs and has to be designed so as not to overfit to any particular type of attack generator during the training process.

C. Robust Architectures, Ensembles, and Cross-Dataset Validation

Authors in [37] propose a framework platform that, among other things, provides an adversarially robust, real-time DDoS detection system based on AutoML to select robust ensembles and validate them against adversarially perturbed traffic, achieving greater than 95 % accuracy under attack while satisfying latency constraints. The following are other works based on Transfer Learning and cross-dataset validation to maintain robustness under changing traffic patterns [38].

Highlighting fragility by LSTM + GAN stress-testing via adversarial neural networks to push for stronger defenses [34]. Other defenses are based on robust architectures and validation strategies in which:

- (i) Ensemble of diverse DL models to decrease the sensitivity to any single feature set,
- (ii) AutoML-based selection of architectures under robustness constraints,
- (iii) Cross-dataset training and evaluation (e.g., training on CIC-DDoS2019 and testing on BoT-IoT or real traces) to assess generalization.

Empirical evidence would support the statement that these innovations indeed enhance resilience against shifts in distribution; however, currently, only a subsection of them considers adaptive adversaries explicitly. A standardized robustness evaluation protocol for DDoS detectors-reporting accuracy under attack, attack success rate, and trade-offs with clean performance-is still missing.

D. Interplay Between XAI and Adversarial Robustness

The two concepts of XAI and adversarial robustness are strictly tied together. To explain, the explanation tools may help the defenders understand which features are critical and, thus, should be protected or monitored; they also detect suspicious changes in model behaviour over time. Conversely, attackers may use explanations to gain knowledge about the most influential features so that they can carry out efficient

adversarial perturbations. Therefore, the DDoS detection systems must be designed under white-box assumptions about robustness: if importance is observable for partial sets of features, evasion should be difficult for the perpetrator. Among the exciting areas for research are:

- (i) Use XAI for robust feature engineering (favour stable and hard-to-manipulate features);
- (ii) Detect adversarial or poisoned inputs using abnormal explanation patterns; and
- (iii) Multi-objective optimization of performance, interpretability, and robustness.

Figure 7 above demonstrates the bidirectional position of XAI in DDoS/IDS-based deep learning: on the left side, XAI aids defense through feature selection improvement and pruning [28]. XAI application to be interpretable

Fig. 7. Dual role of XAI in DL-based DDoS/IDS: defensive

architecture and operator trust [29], [30], and [31] includes explanations through temporal pattern and zero-day detection based on explanation-space anomalies [32], [33]. On the contrary, besides communicating attacks, XAI can be "misused" into adversarial means [35] to spot highly influential features and build upon them for constructing more challenging evasion attacks, which raises a dual-use concern for the explanation tools.

Deep-learning-based DDoS detection has been steadily evolving along an interesting trajectory between 2020 and 2025, with relevant milestones displayed in this timeline figure 8. Early research around 2020 first concentrated on standard architectures like CNNs and RNNs with the aim of attaining high detection accuracy. An increasing influence of adversarial defenses began with GANs in 2021, mainly to counter the evolving DDoS attacks. 2022 saw the appearance of hybrid and collaborative LSTM models along with the first inklings of federated learning, explainable AI (XAI), and explanation-space analysis. In 2023, a marked shift arose toward XAI-based analysis in LSTM-based multi-class DDoS detection. Research in 2024 extended to federated XAI frameworks, GAN-based data augmentation, and robust AutoML ensembles.

Figure 8. Timeline of DL- DDoS Detection Research from Accuracy-focused to XAI and Robustness

Finally, indications for the road ahead in 2025 signal the emergence of Transformer neural networks, temporal explanations, and even explanation-aware attack strategies, identifying an advanced and adversarially aware research landscape.

VII. OPEN PROBLEMS AND RESEARCH CHALLENGES

From the taxonomy and deep analysis, several challenges come to the surface:

1. **Undivided Optimization of Accuracy-XAI-Robustness:** Rather than optimizing accuracy, most works co-opt only one of either XAI or robustness in the ensemble. Hence, there is an immediate need for frameworks that co-existent and explicitly trade and co-optimize the three, along with formal evaluation metrics.
2. **Standardized Adversarial Testing for DDoS Detectors:** The community does not have common benchmarks or threat models to test DDoS detectors under reconnaissance conditions. Hence, a reproducible protocol like FGSM/PGD-style attacks under valid network constraints, attacking with GANs, and cross-dataset shifts has to be developed.
3. **Faithful and Efficient Explanation:** Most XAI methods remain post-hoc and even unwhole-truths or inefficient for near-real-time high-speed networks. Thin, intrinsically interpretable architectures need research into lightweight applicability at the edge/MEC nodes for online detection.
4. **Realistic and Evolving Datasets:** Current datasets are often deficient in new attack campaigns, encrypted traffic patterns, or lengthily time drift. The curating and sharing of such realistic, labeled, and incremental DDoS datasets would be, certainly, necessary for assessing robustness over time and explainability.
5. **XAI-Aware Threat Models:** If such explanations were made publicly available (to dashboards, APIs, or even logs), then attackers could adapt accordingly. Future work should model "XAI-aware adversaries" and construct resilient defenses in cases where partial internal logic is observable.

6. **Integration into Operational Workflows:** Real-life implementations would entail integrations with SDN controllers, cloud orchestrators, and SOC tooling. Liquid explanations, manageable false-positive behavior, and solid efficiency under load are pressing engineering challenges.

This collection of open problems provides a vast future research agenda and motivates hybrid approaches combining optimization, DL, XAI, and adversarial ML.

DL-based DDoS detection research evidently inclines towards standard, high accuracy models, as shown starkly in the proposed taxonomy in Table 3, while only partly and in fragments addressing explainability and robustness dimensions. CNN- and RNN/LSTM-based approaches (e.g., [7], and [8]) dominate the Standard DL column, while XAI has been explicitly integrated only into a limited subset of recurrent and hybrid models (e.g., [28], [30] and [31]) and into interpretable architectures such as K–A networks (e.g., [29]). Robustness-related work is likewise concentrated within a narrow slice of the design space, mainly GAN-based and AutoML/ensemble methods (e.g., [5], [15], [16] and [37]). Most importantly, the XAI + Robustness column is almost entirely empty ("Gap" or "Few" for most model families), which indicates that very few studies try to jointly design DDoS detectors that are accurate, explainable, and adversarial robust. This imbalance serves to reinforce the central research gap that this survey targets and to motivate future work on unifying architectures that integrate explicit XAI strategies and robustness-enhancement techniques across different deep learning families rather than considering these properties in isolation.

Table 3. DL-based DDoS detection by model family, XAI and robustness gap

Model family	Standard DL (no explicit XAI/robustness)	XAI-enhanced	Robustness-enhanced	XAI + Robustness
CNN	[8]	Few / none	None	Gap
RNN / LSTM	[7]	[30] and [31]	None	Gap
Autoencoder (AE)	[6]	–	–	Gap
GAN-based	–	–	[5], [16] & [15]	Few
Transformer	[20]	Implicit attention [20]	–	Gap
Hybrid / Ensemble	[21]	[28]	[37]	Few
Interpretable (K–A)	–	[29]	–	Gap

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This survey revisits, for the first time at the date of drafting, the concept of DDoS detection through modernized lenses, where explainability and adversarial robustness are given more weight than ordinary metrics in measuring the performance. The resultant classification is a three-dimensional taxonomy encompassing the six principal families of models, along with an analysis of how new works (2020-2025) either embrace or neglect an XAI and robust mechanism. Although

DL detectors perform consistently well relative to their accuracy on benchmark datasets, synthesis dictates that:

- The integration of explicit XAI is scant but growing through methods such as SHAP, attention, and interpretable architectures;
- While adversarial evaluations do show promise from methods like GAN training, ensembles, and cross-dataset testing, serious adversarial evaluations are the exception and not the rule.
- Very few approaches holistically treat such dimensions as accuracy, transparency, and robustness.

This future system should be designed to be accurate, intelligible to human operators, and robust against adaptive adversaries by default, so that they may advance toward trustworthy DDoS detection in a real-world network. This may all be achieved by systematic integration of XAI, standard adversarial tests, and multi-objective optimizations. The insights and the taxonomy discussed here provide a structured basis for developing and assessing the next generation of smart, explainable, and resilient DDoS defense solutions.

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is a PhD student in Information Technology at the University of Science and Technology in Aden. He has got his Master's degree in Information Technology from Sikkim-Manipal University, India in 2006. He has got his Bachelor's degree in Computer Science from Hadhramout University, Yemen in 2001. His area of interest lies in Machine learning, Deep learning, IoT and Big Data. He can be contacted at email: shami377@gmail.com</p>	
is currently a Professor of Computer Engineering at Aden University in Yemen. He received his Master and PhD degrees in Computer Engineering from Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee 1993, Delhi 1998, respectively. He was the editor-in-chief of Aden University Journal of Information Technology (AUJIT). He is a founding member of the International Center for Scientific Research and Studies (ICSRS). His main research interests are in the fields of ML, Parallel algorithms, and Cybersecurity. He can be contacted at email: m.albadwi@ust.edu , or al_badwi@hotmail.com</p>	